

CURRENT ISSUES USING THE GROUP DISCUSSION METHOD IN TEACHING PHILOLOGY STUDENTS

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Annotation: In this article, the authors share their experience on the methods of conducting group discussions to increase the effectiveness of training, and about the free and prosperous world, the sanctity of the human factor, love, love - love in the lyrical works of Edgar Allan Poe, the great representative of modern American lyric literature. lyric works are analyzed.

Key words: discussion, methods, point of view, goal achievement, problems, topic, research.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mualliflar mashg'ulotlarning samaradorligini oshirishda guruh munozaralarini o'tkazishning metodlari haqida o'z tajribalari bilan o'rtoqlashib, zamonaviy amerika lirik adabiyotining buyuk namoyondasi *Эдгар Аллан По* lirik asarlaridagi ozod va obod el, inson omilining muqaddasligi, sevgi, ishq – muhabbat haqidagi lirik asarlari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: munozara, usullar, nuqtai-nazar, maqsadga erishish, muammolar, mavzu, tadqiq etish.

The constant and dynamic development of higher philological education leads to increased requirements for the training of future teachers. Its success depends not only on the formation of the necessary knowledge and skills in students, but also on motivation, social skills, a value-based attitude towards their specialty, and the development of such qualities as initiative, independence and readiness for effective personal and professional growth.

In the field of future philological activity of students, a lot depends on the teacher's ability to communicate, think freely and critically, and also manage students. Group discussion is one of the methods of the educational process that helps expand students' horizons and develop communication skills. Therefore, research into the possibilities of using this method in preparing students at a pedagogical university seems relevant.

For a clearer understanding of the problem of setting up linguistic analysis, students need to master the ability to independently assimilate educational material, ask questions, defend their position, follow the discussion and summarize what they

hear. The use of group discussion when working with students allows you to develop the ability to communicate, be active, engage in discussions, work in a team, and evaluate various relationships with other people. Group discussion is a group discussion method that allows you to identify the full range of opinions of group members, possible ways to achieve a goal and find a common group solution to a problem. In a group discussion, each group member can have the opportunity to defend their position, discover a variety of solutions and approaches, and ensure a comprehensive study of the subject. In addition, group discussion helps to activate a person's creative potential, his interest in the subject of discussion, is a unique means of cohesion and development of the group, and ensures group adoption of optimal decisions [1, p. 63]. The method of discussion began to take shape in the 30s. XX century The first who began to apply this method in his work was the Swiss psychologist J. Piaget. He proved that through discussion, the child moves away from egocentric thinking and learns to accept the point of view of another person.

Thus, it has been proven that group discussion not only increases the motivation of participants in solving the problems under discussion, but also has a positive effect on managerial and creative decisions in the group [5, p. 98].

Discussion methods are a type of active social-psychological learning methods based on group communication in the process of solving educational and professional problems. These methods are used when discussing complex theoretical and practical problems, for exchanging life experiences, for clarifying and coordinating the opinions of discussion participants, for developing a single optimal solution, etc.

The possibilities of using the group discussion method in teaching philology students were considered by I.Yu. Abedkovskaya, G.A. Emelyanova, I.L. Kravtsova, N.G. Maltseva, I.V. Orlova, N.V. Orlova, T.V. Pinchuk, T.V. Potylkina and others.

Discussions perform a number of functions: improving and consolidating knowledge; increase in the volume of new information; developing the ability to argue, prove, defend and defend one's opinion, as well as listen to the opinions of others [2, p. 234]. The object of discussion is various problems and cases from professional practice. The subject of discussion is interpersonal relationships between group members. Discussions can be classified on various grounds. According to structure, they are distinguished: structured and unstructured (N.V. Semilet).

According to the nature of the material being discussed: thematic, biographical, task-oriented and interactive discussions (D. Kipper) [3, p. 36].

According to the presence of a leader: discussions with a clear leader, discussions without a leader and discussions with a variable leader (V.P. Zakharov, N.Yu. Khryashcheva) [4, p. 43]. The classification according to M. R. Bityanova presents the following types of discussions: general, ranking in two circles, scale discussion, with observers, discussion with rotation [2, p. 240].

In each discussion, all participants are divided into roles: the moderator-organizer organizes the discussion of the issue, problem and promotes the active involvement of absolutely all group members in it; the analyst asks questions to the participants in the discussion, questions the theories and ideas expressed; the protocol taker records all stages of the discussion and, at the end of the discussion, sums up the results and forms an idea of the opinion of his group; the observer evaluates the participation of each group member in an active discussion. Conducting a group discussion includes several stages. Let us consider them using the example of using the group discussion method when conducting a lesson with first-year students in the academic discipline “Foreign Literature”.

1. Selecting a topic. When choosing a topic, it should be borne in mind that it should not only be relevant, but also consistent with real practice. It should be sufficiently familiar to students and contain problematic questions that would arouse active interest among students. The topic should be formulated clearly, clearly and concisely. It should attract attention and make you think about the problem at hand. For example, “Edgar Allan Poe – America's Freedom Singer.” Students must, a few days before the discussion, know the topic, the questions proposed for discussion, read additional literature on the chosen topic, consult with the teacher, analyze the various points of view of scientists, compare them and determine their own position regarding the proposed issues. In particular, students should know: what works of Edgar Allan Poe are dedicated to the Motherland?, Which wave-loving lyrics of the poet became masterpieces of world literature?

2. Developing questions for discussion. Questions should be formulated from different points of view and be thought-provoking. The wording may contain opinions that are not indisputable, and may contain provisions that contradict facts and differ from the generally accepted interpretation.

3. Development of a discussion script. The scenario includes: an introductory speech from the leader (the rationale for choosing the topic, its relevance and the tasks facing the discussion participants); questions for discussion, conditions for discussion; techniques for activating students (visual aids, technical means, etc.); list of references [2]. An example of an introductory word: “Edgar Allan Poe is a great creator of world literature. He left behind a huge artistic legacy.” To activate the attention of students, the following are used: a portrait of Edgar Allan Poe, several lyrical works of Edgar Allan Poe, words about famous world writers and poets about Edgar Allan Poe, a photo album telling about the life of the poet, a computer.

4. Directly conducting a group discussion during a training session. In the introductory speech, the presenter recalls the topic, goals and objectives of the discussion, and proposed issues for discussion. Next, the participants are divided into roles - presenter, analyst, protocol taker and observer. After the introductory remarks, the facilitator begins the discussion. The question and criteria for solving the problem are voiced. The presenter gives the floor to those wishing to speak, actively promotes the development of the discussion, and draws all participants into an active exchange of opinions. The leader can ask questions to the participants in the conversation and limit them [2]. During the discussion, the presenter can use various tasks: from the given arguments, choose the one that suits the voiced theses; select additional arguments for the given arguments; extract arguments from materials of basic or additional information; refute the given arguments [2, p. 256].

5. Analysis, summing up the discussion. The presenter sums up the discussion, analyzes the conclusions, emphasizes the main points of the correct understanding of the problem, shows the falsity, fallacy of statements, and the inconsistency of individual positions on specific issues of the topic of dispute. Attention is drawn to the content of the discussion, the accuracy of expression of thoughts, the depth and scientific nature of the arguments, and the correct use of concepts and terms. The ability to answer questions and use various means of discussion is assessed, the most active participants in the discussion are noted, and recommendations are given for further study of the problem under discussion.

A clear distribution of the role of each student in the discussion, definition of the functions of the speakers and a certain order of speech stimulate the completeness and quality of the discussion.

In the first group discussions, the facilitator helps to support the correctness of various points of view, strengthens or weakens one or another point of view, stimulates the discussion participants to express their thoughts, requires accurate reasoned conclusions, and makes a generalization of all the material presented.

At the final stage of the discussion, its results are summed up. The criteria for assessing the discussion are: clarity and persuasiveness of the argumentation of one's point of view; clarity and persuasiveness of counterargumentation; correctness of behavior and the degree of respect for the positions of other participants in the discussion.

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